

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Report LYN, Src family tyrosine-protein kinase: Protein Constructs, Cryo-EM, and Biochemical Assay

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	4067 / E5RJ37/ 2.7.10.2
Authors	Chetan Arya and Andrew Mesecar
Collaborating Authors	
Date Approved by Admin Core	September 22 nd , 2023
Document version	V1
Document version date	September 20 th , 2023
Citation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370789
Affiliations	Purdue University

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disease that progresses with age and is one of the most common forms of dementia. This disease is also associated with cognitive impairment due to the result of neural death in the various areas of the brain [1]. The pathogenesis of AD is associated with neural death caused by Amyloid-beta 1-42 ($A\beta_{1-42}$) and tau hyperphosphorylation [2][3]. The hyperactivity of a non-receptor tyrosine kinase Lyn was observed in the brains of AD patients [4]. Also, Lyn was associated with promoting brain cell death by exposure to $A\beta_{1-42}$ [5]. Lyn is a member of the *Src* family kinases (SFKs) that are well-known for their implication in cell transformations and cancer progression [6]. Recent studies also implicate the role of the Lyn in the progression of the neural death promoted by the $A\beta_{1-42}$ peptide. One such reported interaction is the hyperactivity of Lyn which results in the phosphorylation of Fc γ receptor IIb2 (Fc γ RIIb2). Such studies implicate that Lyn has a crucial role in AD and therefore targeting Lyn with small molecule compounds has potential for new-age treatment options. The goal of this project are to structurally enable Lyn for structure-based drug design and to biochemically and biophysically characterize the interaction of inhibitors with Lyn.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

The SFKs consist of 9 non-receptor tyrosine kinases and are expressed ubiquitously in mammals [6]. LYN is mainly expressed in the hematopoietic system. Lyn has a similar structural

architecture alike to other members of SFKs [7]. The human Lyn gene (LYN) consists of 5 domains and exists in two isoforms [8], [9]. A membrane-associated N-terminal SH4 domain followed by a unique domain (UD), the SH3 and SH2 domains, and a catalytic (SH1) kinase domain at C-terminal. The SH4 region contains the myristoyl and palmitoyl groups in most SFKs, which act as a membrane-anchoring site. The two isoforms A and splice variant B differ by a 21-aa splice in the UD region of Lyn A at position 23 [8]. The functionally different isoforms are a must to study for their association in the intramolecular physiological plasticity and functional activity regarding hyperphosphorylation. The implied association of LYN with Alzheimer's Disease needs improvement in the current understanding. Specifically, the improvement in the structural and functional annotation for the catalytically active protein.

RESULTS

PROTEIN PURIFICATION

The LYN protein was expressed and purified from Baculovirus and Bacterial-based expression systems. Two different plasmid constructs have been cloned for full-length LYN expression and purification. The two primary constructs code for the full-length LYN were purified to a high degree (Figure 1), with a yield of approximately 0.6 mg/L and 2.2 mg/L, respectively.

Figure 1: SDS-PAGE of anion exchange chromatography purified LYN (**Left**) Baculovirus-based LYN expression (**Right**) Rosetta2 (DE3) based purified LYN.

STRUCTURAL DATA

The cryo-EM-based structural determination of Lyn was performed from enzyme expressed and purified from *E. coli*. The purified Lyn protein (2 and 3 mg/mL) was frozen onto holey carbon grids at 4°C with 5- and 10-second blotting time. The grids were screened in Talos Arctica (200kV) cryogenic transmission electron microscope for high-throughput single-particle cryo-EM imaging.

Figure 2: single particle Cryo-EM of Lyn. (A) micrograph of Lyn protein (2 mg/mL), (B) 2D-classification of 16,000 particles.

KINETIC ASSAYS

A real-time kinase assay has been established for Lyn to measure the catalytic activity. The PhosphoSens kinase assay is a label-free fluorescence-based assay to detect the tyrosine kinase activity [10]. A synthetic sensor peptide with an δ -hydroxyquinoline derivative (sulfonamide-oxime, Sox) utilizes the Chelation-Enhanced Fluorescence (ChEF) upon phosphorylation upon coordination with Mg (II). The kinase substrate is highly specific to the LYN tyrosine kinase. The assay is able to detect the kinase activity by the enzyme in a concentration-dependent manner (Figure 2 and Table 1)). It is also able to detect Lyn activity in the presence of various inhibitors.

Figure 3: Kinetics of Lyn kinase protein expressed from *SF9* and *E. coli*. **(A)** real-time substrate-dependent fluorescence record of enzyme assay for Lyn isolated from *SF9* cells. **(B)** real-time substrate-dependent fluorescence of Lyn isolated from bacterial expression system. Michaelis-Menten graph fitting for kinetic parameter determination for **(C)** *SF9* expressed Lyn and **(D)** *E. coli* expressed Lyn.

Table 1: Kinetic parameters of Lyn Kinase

Protein	E_t	K_M	V_{max}	k_{cat}	T_i (°C)
LYN _{R2}	250 nM	93.14 μM	2.08 μM/min	8.32 min ⁻¹	61.3
LYN _{SF9}	20 nM	19.6 μM	3.65 μM/min	182.5 min ⁻¹	60.6

FUTURE PLANS

We are planning to improve the purity of the protein and the preparation of cryo-EM grids to obtain better resolution. We are also planning on significantly increasing the number of crystallization screens to obtain crystals of Lyn for X-ray crystallography. Moreover, as many as thirty compounds have been designed based on the type I and II inhibition modes and kinetic assays will be utilized to measure the modulatory effect of the compounds. These new compounds will be used to co-crystallize with Lyn to aid in optimization of more potent and selective compounds.

CONCLUSION

The biochemical studies presented here allow the comparison of domain-related protein stability and activity differences. Such differences can be further explored as the possibility of developing highly selective and potent inhibitor molecules. While the structural features of the kinase domain have been studied for molecular interactions, the lack of full-length structure limits the scope of variability and designing of novel drug molecules. Since the preliminary work plan has been established in order to achieve above stated goal, it will enable the identification of the new Lyn modulators.

IMPACT

This work has led to a degree of collaboration with the Purdue/Indiana TREAT-AD team, who are also working on PTK2b and Lyn.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cloning and Expression

Expression plasmids for *lyn* (SH4-SH3-SH2-SH1 domains).

Vectors:

- 1) **pFastBacHT-A-LYN** (Baculovirus transfer vector with *N*-terminal 6xHis-TEV tag, Ampicillin-resistance).

The plasmid is recombined with a Baculovirus genome using the Bac-to-Bac system (Thermo), and the DNA is transfected into SF9 cells for virus generation and propagation.

Protein sequence with the tag (Tag sequence underlined; * TEV protease cleavage site)

MSYYHHHHHDYDIPTTENLYFQ*GAMDPEQGDIVVALYPYDGIHPDDLSFKKGEKMKVLEEHGEWWKAKSLLTKKEGFIPSNYVAKLNTLETEEWWFFKDITRKDAERQLLAPGNSAGAFIRESETLKGSFSLSVRDFDPVHGDVIKHYKIRSLDNGGGYYISPRITFPCISDMIKHYQKQADGLCRRLEKACISPKPQKPWKDGSLEAWEIPRESIKLVKRLGAGQFGEVWMGYNNSTKVAVKTLKPGTMSVQAFLEEANLMKTLQHDKLVRLYAVVTREEPIYIITEYMAKGSLLDFLKSDEGGKVLLPKLIDFSAQIAEGMAYIERKNIHRDLRAANVLVSESLMCKIADFGLARVIEDNEYTAREGAKFPIKWTAPEAINFGCFTIKSDVWSFGILLYEIVTYGKIPYPGRTNADVMTALSQGYRMPRVENCPELDYDIMKMCWKEKAEERPTFDYQLQSVLDDFYTATEGYQQQP

Predicted mass: 55403.34 Da

Protein sequence after tag removal:

GAMDPEQGDIVVALYPYDGIHPDDLSFKKGEKMKVLEEHGEWWKAKSLLTKKEGFIPSNYVAKLNTLETEEWWFFKDITRKDAERQLLAPGNSAGAFIRESETLKGSFSLSVRDFDPVHGDVIKHYKIRSLDNGGGYYISPRITFPCISDMIKHYQKQADGLCRRLEKACISPKPQKPWKDGSLEAWEIPRESIKLVKRLGAGQFGEVWMGYNNSTKVAVKTLKPGTMSVQAFLEEANLMKTLQHDKLVRLYAVVTREEPIYIITEYMAKGSLLDFLKSDEGGKVLLPKLIDFSAQIAEGMAYIERKNIHRDLRAANVLVSESLMCKIADFGLARVIEDNEYTAREGAKFPIKWTAPEAINFGCFTIKSDVWSFGILLYEIVTYGKIPYPGRTNADVMTALSQGYRMPRVENCPELDYDIMKMCWKEKAEERPTFDYQLQSVLDDFYTATEGYQQQP

DNA sequence (ORF)

ATGTCGTACTACCATCACCATCACCATCACGATTACGATATCCCAACGACCGAAAACCTGTA
TTTTCAGGGCGCCATGGATCCGGAGCAGGGAGACATCGTAGTTGCCCTATACCCATATGACG
GTATTCATCCGGATGATCTTTCTTTCAAAAAAGGAGAGAAAATGAAGGTTTTAGAGGAACAC
GGTGAGTGGTGAAAGCGAAATCCCTCCTCACAAAGAAGGAAGGCTTCATTCCTAGCAACT
ATGTGGCAAACTAAATACGCTGGAAACCGAGGAATGGTTCTTTAAAGACATTACCCGTAA
GGATGCCGAGCGGCAGCTACTTGCACCCGGCAACTCTGCTGGAGCGTTTCTGATAAGAGAAT
CAGAAACTTTGAAGGGTTCGTTTTATTGTTCGGTTCGAGATTTTGACCCGGTACATGGCGAC
GTCATAAAGCATTATAAAATACGGAGTCTTGACAATGGTGGTACTACATCAGTCCTCGCAT
TACATTCCCATGCATTAGCGATATGATAAAACATTACCAAAAACAGGCTGATGGGTTATGTA
GGCGCTTAGAAAAAGCGTGCATCTCCCCAAGCCGAAAAGCCTTGGGACAAGGATGGATC
CCTCGAGGCTTGGGAGATCCCGAGAGAGTTCGATTAATTGGTAAAGCGGCTCGGTGCAGGG
CAATTCGGAGAGGTGTGGATGGGCTATTATAACAATAGTACCAAAGTAGCGGTCAAACGT
TAAAGCCCGGCACTATGTCCGTCCAAGCATTCTGGAGGAAGCTAACTTAATGAAGACGCTT
CAGCACGATAAGCTTGTTCGCCTGTACGCTGTAGTACCCCGCAAGAGCCAATTTATATAAT
AACTGAGTATATGGCCAAGGGATCGCTCCTTGACTTCCTAAAATCTGACGAAGGGGGAAA

GTCCTGTTACCTAAGTTAATCGACTTCAGCGCACAAATAGCGGAAGGAATGGCTTATATAGA
GAGGAAAAATTACATACATAGAGACCTACGAGCAGCAAATGTACTCGTCTCTGAATCCCTCA
TGTGCAAAATAGCGGATTTTCGGCTTGGCCCGTGTATCGAAGACAACGAATACACAGCCCGT
GAGGGTGCCAAGTTTCCAATCAAATGGACGGCCCCGGAGGCAATTAACCTTGGTTGTTTTAC
CATTAAAGTCAGACGTGTGGAGTTTCGGAATCTTGCTTTATGAAATCGTTACATACGGGAAAA
TTCCTTACCCCGGTTCGACTAATGCTGACGTGATGACGGCGTTGTCACAGGGCTACAGGATG
CCGCGAGTTGAAAATTGTCCAGATGAGCTATATGATATTATGAAGATGTGCTGGAAAGAAA
AGGCGGAGGAGAGACCTACTTTTGGATTACCTGCAGAGCGTGCTAGATGATTTTTACACAGCC
ACAGAAGGGCAGTATCAACAACAGCCCTA

2) **pET28a_LYN** (Bacterial transfer vector with *N*- and *C*-terminus 6x-His and N-terminus
TEV tag. Kanamycin resistance)

Protein sequence with tag (Tag sequence underlined; * TEV protease cleavage site)

MGSSHHHHHSSGENLYFQ*GHMEQGDIVVALYPYDGIHPDDL~~SFKKGEKMKVLEEHGEWWK~~
AKSLLTKKEGFIPSNYVAKLNTLETEEWFFKDITRKAERQLLAPGNSAGAF~~LIRESETLKGSFSL~~
SVRDFDPVHGDVIKHYKIRSLDNGGYYISPRITFPCISDMIKHYQKQADGLCRRLEKACISPKPQK
PWDKDHMLEAWEIPRESIKLVKRLGAGQFGEVWMGYNNSTKVAVKTLKPGTMSVQAFLEEA
NLMKTLQHDKLVRLYAVVTREEPIYIITEYMAKGSLLDFLKSDEGGK~~VLLPKLIDFSAQIAEGMA~~
YIERKNYIHRDLRAANVLVSESLMCKIADFGLARVIEDNEYTAREGAKFPIKWTAPEAINFGCFTI
KSDVWSFGILLYEIVTYGKIPYGRTNADVMTALSQGYRMPRVENC~~PDELYDIMKMCWKEKAE~~
ERPTFDYLQSVLDDFYTATEGQYQQQPLEHHHHHH

Predicted mass: 55689.67 Da

Protein sequence after tag removal:

GHMEQGDIVVALYPYDGIHPDDL~~SFKKGEKMKVLEEHGEWWK~~AKSLLTKKEGFIPSNYVAKLN
TLETEEWFFKDITRKAERQLLAPGNSAGAF~~LIRESETLKGSFSL~~SVRDFDPVHGDVIKHYKIRSL
DNGGYYISPRITFPCISDMIKHYQKQADGLCRRLEKACISPKPQKPWDKDHMLEAWEIPRESIKLV
KRLGAGQFGEVWMGYNNSTKVAVKTLKPGTMSVQAFLEEA~~NLMKTLQHDKLVRLYAVVTR~~
EPIYIITEYMAKGSLLDFLKSDEGGK~~VLLPKLIDFSAQIAEGMA~~YIERKNYIHRDLRAANVLVSE
SLMCKIADFGLARVIEDNEYTAREGAKFPIKWTAPEAINFGCFTIKSDVWSFGILLYEIVTYGKIPY
GRTNADVMTALSQGYRMPRVENC~~PDELYDIMKMCWKEKAE~~ERPTFDYLQSVLDDFYTATEG
QYQQQPLEHHHHHH

DNA sequence (ORF):

ATGGGCAGCAGCCATCATCATCATCACAGCAGCGGCGAGAATCTTTATTTTCAGGGCCA
TATGGAACAAGGAGATATAGTAGTTGCTCTATATCCATACGACGGCATTATCCGGATGACC
TGTCGTTCAAGAAGGGTGAGAAGATGAAAGTTCTGGAGGAGCACGGCGAATGGTGGAAAGC
CAAAGCTTGTTAACCAAAAAAGAAGGTTTTATCCCGAGCAATTATGTCGCGAAGCTGAAC
ACCCTGGAGACGGAAGAGTGGTTCTTCAAGGACATCACCCGTAAAGACGCTGAACGCCAAC
TGCTGGCACCGGGTAACTCCGCGGGTTCGTTTCTGATTCGCGAAAGCGAAACTCTGAAAGGC
AGCTTCAGCTTGTCCGTGCGTGATTTTATGATCCGGTTCATGGTGATGTGATCAAGCACTATAAA
ATCCGCAGCCTCGACAACGGCGGTTATTACATCTCCCCGCGTATTACCTTCCGTGCATCTCT
GACATGATTAAGCACTACCAGAAGCAAGCTGATGGCTTGTGCCGTCGTCTGGAGAAGGCGT
GATTTTCTCCGAAACCGCAGAAGCCGTGGGATAAAGACCATATGCTCGAGGCTTGGGAAAT
ACCCAGGGAGTCAATTAACACTGGTTAAGCGTCTGGGTGCTGGTCAATTTGGCGAGGTGTGGA
TGGGTTATTATAACAACACTCGACCAAAGTGGCCGTGAAGACGTTAAAGCCGGGCACCATGAG
CGTCCAGGCGTTTTTGGAAAGAGGCGAATCTGATGAAGACGTTGCAGCATGACAAATAGTGC
GCTTGTACGCGGTTGTTACTCGCGAGGAGCCGATCTACATTATCACCGAATATATGGCAAAG
GGCAGCCTGCTGGACTTTCTGAAGAGCGATGAGGGTGGTAAAGTGCTCCTGCCTAAACTGAT

CGACTTCTCTGCCAGATTGCGGAAGGCATGGCGTATATTGAACGTAAAACTATATCCACC
GCGATCTGCGTGACGCAAACGTTTTGGTTAGCGAGTCCCTGATGTGCAAAATCGCGGATTTC
GGTTTAGCGCGCGTGATTGAGGACAACGAGTACACCGCGAGAGAGGGCGCTAAGTTTCCGA
TTAAATGGACCGCGCCAGAAGCGATCAACTTCGGCTGCTTCACCATCAAGTCCGACGTTTGG
TCTTTCGGCATTCTTTTGTACGAGATCGTCACCTACGGTAAAATCCCGTATCCGGGCCGTACC
AATGCAGACGTGATGACGGCTCTGAGCCAGGGTTACCGTATGCCGCGTGTGAAAATTGTCC
GGATGAACTGTACGATATTATGAAGATGTGCTGGAAAGAAAAAGCGGAAGAACGTCCGACC
TTTGATTACCTGCAGAGCGTTCTGGACGACTTCTATACTGCTACCGAGGGTCAATACCAACA
ACAGCCGCTCGAGCACCACCACCACCACCTGA

Expression:

1) Baculoviral Protein Expression System: -

The P2 viral stock for Lyn was generated by Genscript (Piscataway NJ.). Expression of Lyn was performed in 2x 500mL in 2L Erlenmeyer flasks. A total of 2 x 10⁶ SF9 cells/mL (Viability >97%) were used for the P2 viral infection at 27°C with supplementation of 100 µg/mL penicillin. The volume of P2 viral stock was adjusted based on the infection equal to the 0.1 multiplicity of Infection (MOI). The viral infection for protein production was carried out for 72 hours in a floor shaker set at 27°C with shaking at 120 rpm. Total cell count, viability, and morphology were monitored to verify the infection and protein expression. Cultures were pooled and transferred into 1L centrifuge bottles and centrifuged at 700*g for 30 min at room temperature. Cell supernatant was decanted into the bottle containing 10% house beach and Alconox™ detergent. Cell pellets were re-suspended in 120 mL buffer (Tris-Cl 25 mM, pH 8.0, NaCl 250 mM, Tween-20 0.2% v/v, TCEP 2 mM, Glycerol 5% v/v) and placed in -80°C for future protein purification. Cell lysate for protein purification was obtained by centrifugation of frozen pellets after thawing at 30,000*g for 45 min at 4°C.

2) Bacterial Protein Expression System: -

The plasmid vector that encodes for LYN was transformed into Rosetta™ 2 (DE3) (Genotype: F⁻ *ompT hsdS_B* (r_B⁻ m_B⁻) *gal dcm* (DE3) pRARE2 (Cam^R)) electrocompetent cells, BL21 derivatives for enhance the expression of eukaryotic proteins by containing rare codons used in *E. coli*. Single colony was picked and transferred into LB media containing 50 µg/mL kanamycin and 37 µg/mL Chloramphenicol at 37°C. The overnight culture was transferred into 2YT media for large-scale expression. The 1L 2YT media supplemented with 50 µg/mL kanamycin and 37 µg/mL Chloramphenicol was inoculated with overnight culture at 37°C. The over-expression of protein was induced by the addition of IPTG (500 µM) when OD_{600nm} reached 0.6-0.8. Later, the media was incubated for 20-24 hours at 18°C with a shaking of 150 rpm. Cell pellets were collected by centrifugating the media in 1L centrifuge bottles at 6000 rpm for 30 min. Cells were washed twice with buffer containing tris-Cl 25 mM, pH 8.0, and NaCl 200 mM. Later, cells were re-suspended in a Lysis buffer for protein purification as mentioned further in this report.

PROTEIN PURIFICATION

Purifications were performed on cell pellets with 1 or 6 liters of expression volume. Pellets were resuspended in lysis buffer (25 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 250 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% v/v glycerol, 2 mM TCEP, 0.2% v/v Tween-20, 50 µg/mL Lysozyme) to a volume of 20 ml per gram expressed cells. The cells were lysed using sonication on ice with 5 seconds on, and 15

seconds off for 15 minutes. Lysate was cleared by centrifugation at 50,000*g for 45 minutes at 4°C.

Pure LYN was obtained in three consecutive chromatographic purification steps. At first, the clear lysate was loaded onto the HisTrap HP column (CV: 5mL). The column was washed with 10 CV wash buffer (25 mM Tris-CL pH 8.0, 250 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole, 0.2% Tween-20, and 2 mM TCEP) and the protein was eluted using gradient elution (10 CV) of elution buffer (25 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 250 mM NaCl, 1000 mM imidazole, 0.2% Tween-20, and 2 mM TCEP). The active fractions were pooled and concentrated to a volume of 1-2 mL by using MilliporeSigma™ Amicon™ Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter (10 MWCO). The concentrated fractions were further injected into a Superdex 200 16/60 column in gel filtration buffer (25 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 25 mM NaCl, 0.2% Tween-20, and 2 mM TCEP). Active fractions were combined. In the final step of purification, pooled fractions were loaded onto an anion-exchange column (MonoQ 10/100 GL) equilibrated with low-salt buffer (25 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 20 mM NaCl, 0.2% Tween-20, and 2 mM TCEP) and protein was eluted with high salt buffer (25 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 1000 mM NaCl, 0.2% Tween-20, and 2 mM TCEP). Active fractions were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and quantified by using the Bradford method.

Mass photometry

Mass photometry was applied to calculate the apparent molecular weight and oligomeric states of Lyn in solution at nM concentrations. A 100 nM protein sample was prepared in PBS buffer at room temperature. 15 µl of PBS buffer was added to the rubber gasket well and the mass photometry lens was focused. Then, 3 µl of 100 nM protein solution was added to the drop and mixed by gentle pipetting. The data was collected for over 1 min and mass was calculated using a calibration curve created with proteins of known molecular weight.

Cryo-EM, Data collection, and processing

Cryo-EM grids (Holey Carbon Coated Grids onto 50 Mesh Nickel 3 mm) were prepared at 4°C with 100% humidity. A 2 -3 mg/ml protein solution was added to the grid. A blotting time ranging from 4-6 sec with mild blotting force was followed by a plunge freeze into the liquid ethane. Grids were transferred and stored in liquid N₂ for future data collection.

PhosphoSens Kinase Assay

The assay was performed in a Corning, low-volume 384-well, black flat-bottom polystyrene NBS microplates (3824) at 30°C. The enzyme assay reaction contains the kinase reaction buffer (50 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 0.1% Brij-35, 100 mM MgCl₂), ATP 1 mM, DTT 1 mM, EGTA 0.55 mM, Kinase substrate 10 µM and enzyme in various concentration (range 2 nM – 15 µM). The reaction was initiated by adding enzyme into the reaction mixture and the enzyme was diluted in dilution buffer (20 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 0.01% v/v Brij-35, 5% v/v Glycerol, 1 mg/mL Bovine Serum Albumin). The reaction was monitored by fluorescence measurements with λ_{ex} at 360nm and λ_{em} at 492nm recorded in kinetic mode (readings every 30 seconds for 30-60 minutes). Inhibitor compounds were added to the reaction mixture to record and analysis of the inhibitory effects of the molecules.

Figure 4: The sequence-based alignment of different members of SFK’s family of non-receptor kinase and domain-architecture of LYN.

Inhibitor	Type	<i>K_i</i> (nM)	<i>V₀</i> (μM/min)
Bosutinib TAD0410368	I	13.1 ± 3.9	6.28 ± 1.9
Saracatinib TAD0000640	I	22.8 ± 2.8	7.4 ± 3.9
Masitinib TAD0410068	II	69.6 ± 8.5	8.8 ± 2.3
Nilotinib TAD0410156	II	333 ± 21	8.65 ± 1.6
Bafetinib TAD0410182	II	6 ± 1.9	6.2 ± 0.7

Figure 5: Inhibitory response of different types of inhibitor compounds specific to Lyn protein. The left panel graph exhibits the inhibitor response for Lyn purified from *E. coli* and the right panel shows the inhibitor response for Lyn purified from SF9 cells.

Figure 6: Quaternary structure analysis of Lyn using mass photometry (REFEYN Inc.). Results suggest that Lyn exists as an octameric state in the given buffer condition.

References:

- [1] K. A. Jellinger, “The neuropathological diagnosis of Alzheimer disease,” *J. Neural Transm. Suppl.*, vol. 5, no. 53, pp. 97–118, 1998, doi: 10.1007/978-3-7091-6467-9_9.
- [2] R. Rajmohan and P. H. Reddy, “Amyloid-Beta and Phosphorylated Tau Accumulations Cause Abnormalities at Synapses of Alzheimer’s disease Neurons,” *Journal of Alzheimer’s Disease*, vol. 57, no. 4. IOS Press, pp. 975–999, 2017, doi: 10.3233/JAD-160612.
- [3] C. Mallozzi *et al.*, “Activation of Tyrosine Phosphorylation Signaling in Erythrocytes of Patients with Alzheimer’s Disease,” *Neuroscience*, vol. 433, pp. 36–41, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2020.02.050.
- [4] C. Holmes and J. Butchart, *Systemic inflammation and Alzheimer’s disease*, vol. 39, no. 4. 2011.
- [5] Y. Gwon *et al.*, “Amelioration of amyloid β -Fc γ RIIb neurotoxicity and tau pathologies by targeting LYN,” *FASEB J.*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 4300–4313, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.201800926R>.
- [6] S. J. Parsons and J. T. Parsons, “Src family kinases, key regulators of signal transduction,” *Oncogene*, vol. 23, no. 48 REV. ISS. 7, pp. 7906–7909, 2004, doi: 10.1038/sj.onc.1208160.
- [7] E. Voisset, F. Brenet, S. Lopez, and P. de Sepulveda, “SRC-Family Kinases in Acute Myeloid Leukaemia and Mastocytosis,” *Cancers (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 7, 2020, doi: 10.3390/cancers12071996.
- [8] J. M. C. Teixeira *et al.*, “The two isoforms of Lyn display different intramolecular fuzzy complexes with the SH3 domain,” *Molecules*, vol. 23, no. 11, 2018, doi: 10.3390/molecules23112731.
- [9] P. M. Weerawarna and T. I. Richardson, “Lyn Kinase Structure, Regulation, and Involvement in Neurodegenerative Diseases: A Mini Review,” *Kinases and Phosphatases*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 23–38, 2023, doi: 10.3390/kinasesphosphatases1010004.
- [10] S. Klüter *et al.*, “Characterization of irreversible kinase inhibitors by directly detecting covalent bond formation: a tool for dissecting kinase drug resistance.,” *Chembiochem*, vol. 11, no. 18, pp. 2557–2566, Dec. 2010, doi: 10.1002/cbic.201000352.